

**CURBING EXAMINATION MALPRACTICES IN SCHOOLS,
THE CHALLENGES OF ISLAMIC STUDIES**

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Abstract

This work attempts to discuss a very sensitive issue, affecting our society i.e. examination malpractice. Generally the work focuses on the meaning of Education, the meaning and nature of examination malpractices, the place of Islamic Studies, on the moral development of students as well as the main causes of examination malpractices. Finally, the role of corporate bodies and government on the eradication of the menace of examination malpractice is examined. The paper concludes by examining the challenges of Examination malpractice in school. The place of Islamic studies as a discipline that is concerned with moral is critically examined. The paper recommends that adequate supervision during examination as well as proper teaching and adequate moral instruction by teacher will go a long way in reducing examination malpractices.

Introduction

Nigerians have discovered the importance of education which makes every parents to give priority attention to education of his or her ward and to acquire certificate. This enable the certificate holders to have access to white-collar jobs and live a better life. Yahaya (1990) and Idowu (1995) are of the opinion that both parents and students at all levels of education devote enormous resources including energy and time to ensure success at any examination. Adeyemoh (1990) opines that students of Islamic Studies like their counterparts in other fields desire at all cost to obtain certificate through any available means i.e. by rigging, by using machineries

to get certificates etc. to secure admission into any tertiary institutions and for better rating on a job. Hence, they rush to pass examination at all cost.

Meaning of Education According to Dictionary

It is a process of teaching, learning and training. Especially in schools or colleges, to improve knowledge and develop skills. This usually takes place at school, colleges or university.

The Concept of Education

There is usually a descriptive definition of a term or a concept Harry School Field calls it "Dictionary Definition" and explains it as a definition" that has been formulated in the past, has become standard, and is accepted as explaining adequately.

Definitions that begin with "education" are said to be descriptive for they describe what education is and not what it should be. The descriptive sense of the term education, describe activities that constitutes the process of educating people. Again when we talk of educational establishment we are describing the College and the Ministry as establishments dealing with activities and process that are educational. The term education is then describing what goes on in these institutions.

The other sense of the term education is prescriptive or normative. The term in the sense refers to what ought to be regarded as education. This means skills and abilities can pass for education only if they conform with our norms or prescription on what we call education. These same norms are used in defining and educating man.

A society of hunters, may, for instance, take education to be efficiency in shooting a fast moving beast with an arrow and a bow. This efficiency becomes the norm used in judging activities or processes as constituting education or not, and not, and in knowing who an educated man is. The aim of education in this society is one that suit its norms. The aim should centre on the production of efficient shots.

Norms that characterize education and the educated man are value loaded and differ from one society to another and from one culture to another. For this, reason attempt to come with a universally acceptable definition of education and of educated

man may be futile. This notwithstanding we should still insist that formulation of aims of education should tally with our conception of education in and out of educated man.

R.S. peter, then, defined an educated man as some one who has satisfied the following criteria.

- (a) That he pursues an activity for its own sake (one should, for example, learn Geography for its value and not for extrinsic reasons).
- (b) That he has understanding of the principles for organizing facts (one should grasp the reason why things are what they are and not just do things mechanically). One should also, be transformed by what one understands.
- (c) That his specialization is not narrow (an educated person, in contrast to a trained person, should have a broad understanding that leads him to view a discipline or an issue in relation to others)

Peters' criteria beg for criticisms. One of such criticisms is that education is not only pursued for its own sake, for if this must be so, lawyer for instance, who learns law for the sake of earring a living remains uneducated even if he practices his profession efficiently.

Secondly, peters criteria only emphasized the cognitive aspect of man and relegated his psycho-motor and affective domains to the background.

As long as norms are used in defining education and the educated man no criterion including those given by R.S. peters or any other person can be universally accepted if there is no consensus of opinion on the criteria to be used in knowing who is an educated person and who is not? It then seem that our concern with aims of education and the means of realizing them is either otiose or constrained by diverse value judgments. We still need to be concerned with the aims of education and we should accept the fact that our analysis of aims as they related to what is education and who is an educated man are subject to our value-judgments.

Value-judgment exist in all the concepts and issues analyzed by philosophy.

Our values differ because- our beliefs in culture and knowledge all differ due to the experience, we acquire from the time we were born to the present. These differences constitute a problem that stop us from getting a unanimous or at least, a generally accepted view or a decision on an issue or concept. This problem will be

confronting us in all the concepts and issue analyzed in the next.

The Holy Prophet Muhammad (S.A.W) says, "Seeking knowledge is a duty on every Muslim man and Woman". Source: Holy Prophet Muhammad (S.A.W) Hadith Quduz.

According to Dictionary: It is a process of teaching, learning and training especially in schools or colleges to improve knowledge and develop skills. This usually takes place at colleges or university.

Taiwo (1980) defined education as the combined efforts of the community to raise the economic society and political standard of life. In general terms, the word education can be said to be an English derivative of the Latin word "Educare" which means to "bring up" lead out or elevate A (Babs Fafunwa). Education therefore, become a very strong instrument for bringing up the youth or helping to elevate their latent potentials thereby making them useful members of the society. In other words, education is the acquisition of knowledge from the day one is born to the day he dies. From the childhood, man starts his education with the mother. Mothers are regarded as first teachers who trained the child from infancy. The holy prophet Muhammad (SAW) laid much emphasis on the choice of a wife, so that the right "teacher" for the children (one child who will impart correct education) is selected by the prospective father. It is the process of leading the individual into the way of the life of the society, the process of initiating him into the society to which he lives, works, and dies.

There are many definition of education as there are educationist, philosophers, scholars and students. That could even be more because a person can define education in more than one way, and from time to time finds the needs to want to change or modify an earlier definition as in the case of Landu B. (2004) who recently admitted that his earlier definition of education was inadequate for his contemporary society. A view of the current definition of education are given thus:-

R.C. Lodge holds the view that life is education and education is life meaning that the process of education spans through a mans life. On the other hand, Plato believed that a good education consisted of giving to body and the soul all the beauty and all the perfection of which they are capable. According to White Head (1950), education is the ant of the utilization of knowledge.

From the above definitions one could see that for any given definition the term is contingent upon who is giving it. This notwithstanding, education can be said to be the development of an independent and integrated, personality. It entails training and acquisition of special skills, knowledge, attitudes and values needed by an individual to be responsible and which would give him room to contribute his own quota to the growth of the society.

Education is a life long process, and aims at imparting the skill needed to live a meaningful lives and for an individual to adjust well to his immediate environment and ultimate world or universe in which he finds himself. It can be said to be the process by which a sound mind in a sound body is developed. For education to be worth its while it must be able to produce a refined mind, body and soul.

The main purpose of education, therefore, is to develop the individuals, so that he can be useful to himself, his family, and the society at large. Development in this case does not only mean physical development that we can always see, but it also include intellectual and emotional development that can only manifest themselves, in the behavior and mental activities of the individual in an age of science and technology. Part of the purpose of education is or, should be, to provide for the individual basic training in science and technology, such that at the end of his training, the individual would serve his nation and use his acquired skill to develop and maintain the tools that are essential for it. A nation that ignores education in science and technology can not be fully developed and the tendency for such a nation to continue to depend on the technology of advance countries for its own industrial and economic development is very high.

Meaning and Nature of Examination Malpractice

Although, one can not talk about the nature of examination malpractice without examining the definition of examination malpractices. This is a form of manipulation that result into false realization of the ability of student, leaving outcome in an examination such a result become deceptive because it is not showing the true ability of the individual. According to Shonekan (1996), examination malpractices can be described as illegal misconduct and improper practices in an

examination with a view to obtain good result through fraudulence. From the above definitions one can see that examination malpractices and negative attitudes, are condemnable in any society. Examination malpractices thus refers to illegal means employed by students in passing an examination in or outside the examination hall.

Examination System

Examination is the pivotal-point around which the whole system of education revolves and the success failure of the system of examination is indeed an indicator of the success or, failure of that particular system of education. It would be pertinent to examine the present system of examination with a view to determining whether it actually serves the purpose it purports to serve. The two basic assumption of any examination worth its name are;-

- (a) It should be valid
- (b) It should be reliable.

The two are distinct concept. An examination is said to be valid if it perform the function for which, it is designed to perform. The system has degenerated to an extent that its validity and reliability are questionable. Examination is no longer regarded as a test for evaluating the performance or judging the scholastic attainment of students.

The reason is that there is a complete break down of the whole system of examination, at all levels of education. The use of unfair means in examination has assumed a dangerous dimension. The educational establishments are experiencing an ever increasing trend towards the use of unfair means in examination. Such establishments are unable to stop this drive. The concerned tiers of government, federal as well as state have realized the problems but not been able to tackle this menace effectively.

The intensity and pervasiveness of this problem can be established from the fact that apart from students some parents too intervene negatively and help to facilitate their children in their cheating adventures. Maduka (1994), contended that the origin of examination malpractice and "expo" in Nigeria can be traced to the parents and private school owners.

Dimension of Examination Malpractice are:

1. By copy of any written value materials into examination hall;
2. By copy one another
3. By leakages of Expo
4. By writing the answers in the sensitive party of their bodies.
5. By browsing on net with their handset phone
6. By employing mercenaries to write for them
7. By buying the questions papers before the exam day
8. By follow up through the lecturers

Factors that Influence Examination Malpractice:

The following among others are the factors that influenced examination malpractices.

- Historical Influence
- Parental Influence
- Historical trends of examination malpractice in Nigeria
- Teacher's Influence

(a) Historical Influence: Historically, examination malpractice is not a new development and it is not peculiar to a particular examination in Nigeria. It cuts across the educational system from primary, post-primary and tertiary levels of our educational system. It involves the candidates, the teacher, the institution and examining bodies.

(b) Influence of Parents: Some parents and guardians have been found to encourage the perpetuation of this ugly act of examination malpractice by their children either directly or indirectly e.g. buying papers from supervisors or collaborating with some school principals.

The pressure from parents and guardians for their children to pass-examination at all cost is tantamount to looking for short cut ways of success. Parents and guardians go to the extent of recruiting impersonators tagged mercenaries to write examinations and procure real question paper for their children. (Landu 2004).

Therefore, both parents and guardians with their relations were said to be aiding examination malpractice in both secular and Islamic school, According to Makanjuola (1999) both parents and guardians were involved in the internal and external examinations. There are many parents that do not have time for their children. They are more concerned with worldly things; the Holy Qur'an said. "The mutual rivalry for pilling up the good things of this world diverts you (from the more serious things) until you visit grave" (chapter 102 vs 1-2).

بِسْمِ اللَّهِ الرَّحْمَنِ الرَّحِيمِ
"الْهَكْمُ التَّكَاثُرُ حَتَّى زُرْتُمُ الْمَقَابِرَ"

(c) **Influence of Teacher:** In the past, teachers were highly devoted to their jobs. They were sustained by the missionary zeal and belief that their reward was in heaven. But nowadays, as a result Nigerian national malaise of materialism, the teachers want their reward here and now like their counterparts in other profession.

Prophet Muhammad says; "The best of you is he who eat from his handwork". Thus, because Prophet Daud was a blacksmith and he eats from his works: Sahihu Bukhari, Vol. II (1998). Today, teachers have lost the sense of pride, because they are no longer satisfied with their condition of services and their status in the social ladder. This state of affairs has adversely affected the teaching profession Obe (1996), also, declared that teachers should master their subject, communicate effectively and not to be rigid in his teaching methods.

(d) **Influence of Examination Bodies:** Since the inception of Examination bodies decades ago their area of responsibilities have been consistently on the increase. For instance such examination bodies as the West Africa Examination Council (WAEC), National Examination Councils (NECO) have enlarged responsibilities such that it is becoming too difficult to

coordinate the large number of students sitting for their examinations and others.

The Challenges of Examination Malpractice:

The challenges of examinations malpractice on quality education at institutions of learning in general and at the primary and secondary schools across the nation in particular are enormous. In consonance with this view, Eweniyi (2002) argued that examination malpractice has become one of the greatest problems undermining the very foundations of education practice.

According to Makanjuola, (1990) most perpetrators of malpractices who escape being detected and manage to get admitted into higher institutions may likely obtain a certificate which they might not be able to defend. The use of unfair means in examination in certain areas has indeed become a thriving business for the examination media.

Sample and Sampling Techniques

Simple random sampling techniques was employed to select respondent from the taught population of the selected secondary schools in Ilorin West Local Government Area of Kwara State.

Four (4) secondary schools were selected out of secondary schools in the Local Government Area.

The schools selected using the sample random sampling techniques;

1. Ansarul-Islam Secondary School Ogidi Ilorin
2. Government High School Adeta Ilorin (G.H.S)
3. Ilorin Grammar School (I.G.S)
4. College of Arabic & Islamic Studies Adewole (CAIS) Ilorin

All the schools are co-educational from the total population and students in Junior and Senior classes in each selected school were randomly chosen by making each of them tick the appropriate answers.

The challenges of this works presents result and discussion as obtained from field survey. This basically deals with the analysis of data collected from the set of instrument used for the study.

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This works presents results and discussion as obtained from field survey. This basically deals with the analysis of data collected from the set of instrument used for the study.

Data Analysis

Simple percentage analysis was carried out showing proportional percentage and explanation given where necessary. This applies to all the Nine (9) items on the questionnaire. All the items were divided into two tables in order to show the various aspect examined.

Item	Agree	Disagree	Total
1. Examination malpractices are once and done in every school.	88	44	132
2. External malpractices are common in every school.	120	30	150
3. Malpractices in examination are common in every school.	104	83	187
4. The high cost of examination malpractices is a major challenge to schools.	133	30	163
5. Malpractices in examination are common in every school.	130	40	170
6. Malpractices in examination are common in every school.	130	40	170
7. Malpractices in examination are common in every school.	130	40	170
8. Malpractices in examination are common in every school.	130	40	170
9. Malpractices in examination are common in every school.	130	40	170
Total	130	40	170

Table 1: Responses on Malpractices in Examination

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Title 1: Responses on Factors Responsible for Examination Malpractice in Some Selected Schools Examination

S/N	STATEMENT	S.A		A		D		N		Remarks
		NF	STRONGLY AGREE	%	AGREE	%	DISAGREE	%	NEUTRAL	
1.	Non-challant attitude of Teacher could encourage examination malpractice.	200	130	65.3	40	20	30	15	-	100
2.	The high cost of registering students for external examination could aid examination malpractice.		133	66	30	15	35	17	2	100
3.	Over crowding in the examination hall make it easy for people to copy from each other.		164	82	15	7.2	10	5	-	94.2%
4.	Lack of enough invigilation contributes to examination malpractice.		150	75	30	15	10	5	5	75
5.	Below average student are the ones who engage in examination malpractice.		88	44	60	30	40	20	6	-

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Data Analysis

Simple percentage analysis was carried out showing proportional percentage and explanation given where necessary. This implies all items on the questionnaires. The items were divided into three.

A total of 200 questionnaire were distributed to students and 196 were retrieved from the respondents inferences could be draw from the receive questionnaire of the respondents. Therefore, it could be noticed in statement that 130 students strongly agreed that the non-challant attitude of teachers could encourage examination malpractice. This represent 66.3% or 130 out of the total participants 40 student which represents 20% say what? While 30 students disagreed and it represent 15%.

Statement two (2) 133 students conceded to the fact that high cost of registering students for external examination could aid examination malpractice. This makes 66% as against 15% 35 students agreed and 35 students disagreed representing 17% respectively.

In statement (3) 115 students responded that the usage of technical language for teaching and learning affects understanding and thereby aid examination malpractice. 50 students agreed, this represents 25% and 59 respectively = 7.5%.

Similarly 120 students strongly agreed with the statement that parent enforced their children to do certain courses thereby encourage examination malpractice, while about 30% agreed, this represents 30% and 15% respectively.

40% of which is 96 students strongly agreed that they feel disappointed when they discovered that they were fully in an examination and this could encourage examination malpractice. 50 students agreed which represent 25% of the total disagreed score percentage.

In the affirmative response, 115 students gave an affirmative response for a student that has an incomplete note and this makes 33.4% while 30 students disagreed which represent 15%.

In table two (2) 66 students responded that it is due that insufficient time to read for examination could encourage examination malpractice. 25% agreed which represent

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Title 1: Responses on Factors Responsible for Examination Malpractice in Some Selected Schools Examination

S/N	STATEMENT	NF	S.A	STRONGLY AGREE	%	A	AGREE	%	D	DISAGREE	%	N	NEUTRAL	%	Remarks
1.	Emphasis placed on certificate towards employment and admission into higher institution contributes to examination malpractice.	200	135	67.5	43	21	25	12.5	100						
2.	None usage of local languages or teaching and learning understanding lead to examination malpractice.		115	57.5	50	25	15	7.5							-89
3.	Parents enforcing courses on their children and this could encourage examination malpractice.		120	60	60	30	10	5							95
4.	Parents fee disappointed when their wards fail in an examination could lead to cheating in an examination.		98	40	65	32.5	50	25							97

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164 students strongly agreed overcrowding in the spacing of examination hall make it possible for people to copy from each other 10 other students disagreed representing 5% respectively.

The assertion that not having enough invigilators is a possible cause of examination in statement 4 was strongly agreed by students, a total of 150 students strongly agreed while 30 agreed and 10 students disagreed. These make 75% respectively.

The average students below are the ones who engage in examination malpractice, 88 students strongly agreed that below average students are the ones who engage in examination malpractice. These make 44% as against 30 students who just agreed while 40 students disagreed and 65 students which constitutes 6%, however remained neutral.

The above 196 respondents gave an affirmation to the fact that the emphasis placed on the certificate towards employment and admission into higher institutions, contributes to examination malpractices. The number of the respondent (200) stated for this represent 67.5 and 43 students agreed which make 21% disagreed.

In statement (2) 115 students responded that no usage of local language for teaching and learning affects understanding and thereby aid examination malpractice. 50 students agreed, this represents 25% and 7.59 respectively = 7.5%

Similarly 120 students strongly agreed with the statement that parent enforced their children to do certain courses thereby encouraging examination malpractice, while about 30% agreed, this represents 5% and total percentage in 95%

40% of which is 98 students strongly agreed that parent feel disappointed when they discovered that they fail woefully in an examination and this could encourage examination malpractice, 50% disagreed which represent 25% of the total disagreed score percent 5age is 97.5%.

In the affirmative response out of the 196 respondent 78 students gave an affirmative response as to the fact that it is possible for a student that has an incomplete note and time to pass. This represent 39% 68 students gave negative, this makes 334% while 24% remain neutral.

In table two(2) 66 students responded that it is true that insufficient time to read for examination could lead to response while 27.5% agreed which represent

2.7%.

The claim that poor invigilation leads to examination malpractice was strongly agreed while agreed is 65 also 15 students disagreed which representing 32.5% and 7.5 respectively.

The statement which states that it is right to avoid multiple set of examination i.e. for science students so as to discourage them from area of concentration in examination malpractice has strongly agreed of 57 students representing 28.5% and agreed too by 50 students representing 25.5% while 40 disagreed to make 20%.

Effects of Examination Malpractice: It discourage good candidate from studying hard. Good candidates are to believe that if you can not beat them you join them. Especially, as they see other candidates get away with their corrupt behavior. These behaviours may be contagious as more and more candidates tend to join in examination malpractice. They believe that the end will justify the means. Many good students have been denied admission by the corrupt ones who through examination malpractice have scored good grades. The best brain that could help in research and development are likely to be thrown out or frustrated while seeking admission.

Every year many students are caught for engaging in examination malpractice which need to be investigated before results are released. Though some results are with held, or pending, the determination of the cases some are decided before results are released.

Islamic point of views on examination malpractice and the evils of examination malpractice. According to the Quran 61 vs 1-2 says. (What ever is in the heaven and on earth let it declare the praises and Glory of Allah: he is the Exalted in might the Wise.

يأيها الذين آمنوا لم تقولون ما لاتفعلون كبر مقتا عند الله أن تقولوا ما لاتفعلون

Oh ye who believe why say ye that which ye do not)? Moreover over Allah (S.W.T.) Says in chapter 3 vs 188.

ولاتحسبن الذين يفرحون بما أتوا ويحبون أن يحمدا بما لم يفعلوا فلا تحسبنهم

بمفازة من العذب ولهم عذاب اليم.

Think not that those who exult in what they have brought about and love to be praised for what they have not done; think not that they can escape the penalty. For them is a penalty glorious indeed.

Recommendations

There are some possible solutions to the challenges of malpractice, one of which is that continuous assessment should be conducted for students to assist them with good grades in the exams. This will reduce examination malpractices since 40% of marks are accumulated from various assessment techniques such as projects before actual exams. Apart from normal invigilators/supervisors examination officers heads of department, lecturers should make official visit to the examination halls in order to observe the behaviors and attitudes of students while writing the exam.

Other possible solution to curb examination malpractices is that examination bodies i.e. WAEC, NECO, and other bodies. Government should establish examination codes and ethics committees in all the state of federation. The study of religion particularly Islamic studies should be made compulsory in our schools, because "the fear of God is the beginning of wisdom". A students that morally and spiritually sound will not indulge in any examination malpractice. Teachers of Islamic studies should also serve as role model, they should not indulge in aiding malpractice; rather they should be seen at all time as working to stop this ugly incidence. It is high time, that government at all levels deemphasized the high premium place on paper qualification. There should be oral interview and written test to boast the qualification for any placement for appointment. Admission should be based on practical or aptitude test in order to determine competency and potentialities. Once this is adopted, hustle for examination malpractice in order to pass examination at all cost will be reduced, more so, the Parent Teachers Association (PTA) should be more concerned about this problem as stake holders. They should work hand in hand with the school administration. They should set up examination and ethics committees. This committee will write a report of their observation and submit to the school management after the examination. This will go a long way to

correct the errors of the school concerned.

Teacher's poor handling of their subjects was seen as a major cause of examination malpractice. Teachers are encouraged to use appropriate methodology and cover the required section before examination. During examination, students should not be allowed to be in many examination halls while adequate supervision should be provided.

Summary of findings

The following facts emerge from the findings of this study to be responsible for examination malpractice in secondary school visited:

1. Ansarul Islam secondary school Ogidi Ilorin
 2. Government high school Adeta Ilorin (G.H.S)
 3. Ilorin grammar school (I.G.S) Ilorin
 4. College of Arabic and Islamic studies Adewole, Ilorin (C.A.I.S)
 - a. Non-challant attitude of teacher could encourage examination malpractice.
 - b. The high cost of registering students for external examination aid examination malpractice.
 - c. Over crowding in examination hall makes it possible for students to copy from each other.
 - d. Lack of invigilation is a possible cause of examination malpractices
 - e. Emphasis placed on certificate towards employment and admission into her higher institution contributes to examine malpractice.
 - f. Parents enforcing course of study on their children also, encourage examination malpractice.
 - g. It is possible students who has incomplete note indulge in cheating during examination.
 - h. Teacher giving area of concentration also lead to examination malpractice
 - i. In adequate preparation for examination could lead to examination malpractice.
- More so, parents who imposes course of study on their wards and the value place on educational certificate by the society contribute immensely to examination malpractice. Despite that, examination malpractice is an act which contravenes the

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rule and regulations of examination and this is not in consonance with the smooth running of an examination.

Invigilators should take proper care to examine their works correctly and or see that the efficiency of their duty are carried out. All those concerned, i.e. H.O.D supervisor, head masters should pay regular and unexpected visits to schools in order to observe their bad characters among them and to bring normal and unacceptable way back to the school.

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